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TOM 2

AKTUALNE PROBLEMY BADAWCZE NAUKI SPOŁECZNE I HUMANISTYCZNE

nauki ekonomiczne | nauki humanistyczne | nauki polityczno-prawne
nauki społeczne i pedagogiczne | nauki teologiczne

**Aktualne problemy badawcze.
Tom 2.
Nauki społeczne i humanistyczne**

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LEGAL ASPECTS OF MANDATORY VACCINATION IN THE EUROPEAN UNION

Introduction

Outbreaks of infectious diseases in the European Union (EU), exacerbated by the coronavirus pandemic (COVID-19), have sparked discussions regarding the necessity for effective reformation of the EU health system, including anti-epidemic control and prevention. Vaccination is one of the most efficient ways to protect the health of each individual and society as a whole. Although vaccination of the population is a fairly common preventive medical intervention, it is accompanied by side effects, prompting governments to strike a balance between public health and individual rights. Propaganda against vaccination and speculation about the public's ignorance of its consequences do not improve the situation.

There is a disputable legal issue concerning balance between the private interest of the person who does not want to be vaccinated and the interest of that part of society that may consider the unvaccinated person as a danger.

What's more, Emergency Use Authorization (EUA) should also not be ignored. EUA is a mechanism that promotes the availability and use of drugs, vaccines or other medical immunobiological drugs during emergencies. EUA allows for the temporary use of a medicine under specific conditions as long as emergency circumstances apply. The medicine however remains unlicensed and cannot be put on the market, contrary to a (conditional) marketing authorization.

Literature review: Comparative analysis of the author's native Ukrainian (Demchenko, Dubytska 2017; Kruglova 2011; Gubanova 2017; Senuyta 2009) and European (Sturgis et al. 2021; Savulescu 2021) legal literature allowed to reach some convincing conclusions on this issue, but such conclusions are mostly characterized by significant subjectivity and "human-centeredness", that is understandable considering flaws of Ukrainian legislation, which should be reformed in favor of societal interests.

Some scientists maintain the position that this medical intervention is a personal right (Demchenko, Dubytska 2017), therefore the state should use all legal instruments to protect it. Others scientists (Gubanova 2017; Senuyta 2009; Sturgis et al. 2021; Savulescu 2021) consider that an unvaccinated person is a danger to society, which puts others at risk, and therefore see it as a duty of a citizen who has no medical contraindications to be vaccinated.

The legal community has drowned into discussion that has been provoked by the decision of the European Court of Human Rights (hereinafter – “the ECtHR”) in the case “Vavříčka and Others v. the Czech Republic” of April 8, 2021, the decision of which clearly follows the position of the ECtHR on vaccination.

The case raises the question: is vaccination an individual right or an obligation? The author presents his own perspective on the doctrine of natural law and the ECtHR practice concerning the content of the right to get vaccinated and the legal consequences for a person in the event of side effects via methods of empirical research (comparison); and methods of theoretical research (abstraction, analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, ascent from the abstract to the concrete).

Aim of the study

In this article I analyze vaccination from the point of the right and the duty of a person by analyzing ECtHR case law concerning the content of the right to get vaccinated and legal consequences for its side effects.

Materials and Methods

The author presents his is own perspective on the doctrine of natural law and the ECtHR practice concerning the content of the right to get vaccinated and the legal consequences for a person in the event of side effects via methods of empirical research (comparison); and methods of theoretical research (abstraction, analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, ascent from the abstract to the concrete).

Results

Article 10 of the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, signed in 4 November 1950, states that everyone has the right to freedom of opinion and expression (a person may present arguments against vaccination – the

author's position). This also applies to professional statements in the medical field is evidenced by the decision in the case "Frankovicz v. Poland" no. 53025/99, where the ECtHR stated that accusation and disciplinary action for making critical comments about the nature of a patient's treatment is tantamount to interfering with the exercise of the right to freedom of expression.

Paragraph 11 of Part 1 of the European Social Charter proclaims the right of everyone to benefit from any measures enabling to enjoy the highest attainable standard of health. Therefore, we understand that each person has the right to support mandatory vaccination or, vice versa, to present its own opinion and arguments as to why such a procedure is illegal.

In some cases, the ECtHR has indirectly admitted the absolute right to vaccination.

In "Pretty v. The United Kingdom" no. 2346/02 the ECtHR determined that in the provision of medical care, even when the denial of a particular treatment could be fatal, involuntary medical treatment without the consent of the able-bodied patient is an infringement of his or her physical integrity and the rights guaranteed by Article 8 of the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms. Thus, this view of the ECtHR reinforces the arguments against mandatory vaccination.

In "Jehovah's Witnesses of Moscow and Others v. Russia" no. 302/02 the ECtHR also pointed out that in order to preserve the freedom to refuse treatment, it is necessary to ensure the patient's right to make decisions in accordance with his own views and values, no matter how irrational, unreasonable and short-sighted they may seem to others.

In the context of the article, the stance of the ECtHR is relevant: a state may interfere in the freedom of choice of citizens in the field of health care, if there are signs of the need to support the interests of third parties.

Opponents of vaccination refer to "Jehovah's Witnesses of Moscow and Others v. Russia" no. 302/02, but ignore the fact that the case concerned the refusal of members of the religious organization Jehovah's Witnesses from blood transfusions in emergencies, rather than aspects of vaccination. Moreover, in the present case the ECtHR recognized the supremacy of the private interest over the public one, which is not applicable to the case-law regarding the right to vaccination.

When it is necessary to determine the measures of "right to get vaccinated" we should be guided by principle *lex specialis derogat generali* – preference in the interpretation and application of general and special rules of law should be given to special rules, as health care rules apply to completely different spheres of life. legal nature (different regulation by regulations, grounds and exceptions, etc.). The analysis of the "right to vaccination" should not be guided solely by general norms in the field of health care, as their consideration without further reference to special norms will distort the reader's impression of mandatory vaccination, and prevent the state from pursuing public interests, even when the latter are lawful and justified within the special rules of law.

Let us address to the works of scholars of natural law doctrine (as their works are based on fundamental acts of international law such as the Convention for the Protec-

tion of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms) who spoke of the restricted nature of human rights and freedoms.

As Montesquieu (1748) noted, "If a citizen could do what the laws forbid, he would be no longer possessed of liberty, because all his fellow-citizens would have the same power".

According to Article 29 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and Article 4 of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, human rights' restrictions should be imposed only in so far as this may be compatible with the nature of these rights and solely for the purpose of promoting the general welfare in a democratic society.

The ECtHR has also developed meaningful practices on human rights restrictions. In "Savin v. Ukraine" no. 34725/08 it is determined that for the necessity in a democratic society intervention appropriate motives must be appropriate, sufficient, and justify the restriction of individual rights, the relevant decision-making process is fair and able to ensure adequate protection of interests.

Therefore, vaccination of a person against diseases that are mandatory for WHO recommendations and relevant national health standards is a duty in most developed countries, as evidenced by international practice. There is no univocal vaccination policy in the European Union, but it is up to each country to decide which vaccine will be mandatory or not. At the same time, countries such as France, Italy, the Czech Republic, Bulgaria, Croatia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Poland and Latvia introduced mandatory vaccinations against tetanus, diphtheria, pertussis, haemophilia, hepatitis B, poliovirus, mumps, measles and rubella.

American human rights' scientist Juan I. Acosta (2015) cites 4 criteria which justify mandatory vaccination.

1. Legitimate goal. A mandatory vaccination policy, which restricts informed consent, personal integrity and the right to privacy, would have to be articulated under a clear purpose, such as the eradication of a specific epidemic, and not just generally for the prevention of disease.
2. Provided by law. As the Inter-American Court of Human Rights has affirmed, the word law for the legitimate restriction of rights means a general legal norm tied to the general welfare, passed by democratically elected legislative bodies established by the Constitution, and formulated according to the procedures set forth by the constitutions of the States Parties for that purpose.
3. Strict necessity. The risk to the public must be probable and not merely speculative or remote.
4. Proportionality. In order to restrict human rights, a coercive approach might be sustained only when there is an individual determination that the person poses a significant risk to the public. The risk to the public must be probable and not merely speculative or remote.

While pursuing a policy of mandatory vaccination at the national level, a state should verify its introduction in accordance with the above criteria if it wants to en-

sure an adequate balance between public health at the community level and the rights of the individual.

The practice of the ECtHR is solid. At first glance, there are certain cases expressed in cases such as “*Pretty v. The United Kingdom*” no. 2346/02, “*Jehovah’s Witnesses of Moscow and Others v. Russia*” no. 302/02, however, they do not directly concern the essence of the right to get vaccinated and recourse to them to justify absolute freedom of vaccination is incorrect.

If the preliminary conclusions have been formed before the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, the case “*Vavříčka and Others v. the Czech Republic*” (nos. 47621/13 and 5 others) of 8 April 2021 is unique and extremely relevant, as for the first time in its history the ECtHR has recognized the mandatory vaccination of children.

In the case, the first applicant was fined for failing to vaccinate his two children in the Czech Republic. All other applicants were denied admission of their children to kindergarten for the exact reason. The main problem was the necessity for the authorities to take action against the applicants in support of vaccination policy and whether it violated the plaintiffs’ right to privacy within the meaning of Article 8 of the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms.

The decision on the children of Czech citizens is consistent with the ECtHR’s position in *Kokkinakis v. Greece* no. 14307/88: the applicants’ right to physical integrity was restricted in order to “preserve the health of all persons, and especially those vulnerable to certain diseases”.

In “*Vavříčka and Others v. the Czech Republic*” (nos. 47621/13 and 5 others) the ECtHR ruled that states have an obligation to put the best interests of children at the heart of all decisions affecting their health and development: if voluntary vaccination policies are insufficient to achieve and maintain collective immunity, or collective immunity does not help due to the nature of the disease, states have the right to introduce a policy of mandatory vaccination in order to achieve an adequate level of protection against such diseases. Regarding the non-admission of unvaccinated children to educational institutions, the judges noted that such measures are protective, not punitive.

In this case, ECtHR’s position is similar to John Locke’s one, who stated that the “purpose of the law should be not the abolition or restriction of freedom, but on the contrary - its preservation and development of the rights of society”. The ECtHR ruled that the benefits of vaccination outweigh any possible risks of side effects.

Furthermore, EUA is also necessary for EU, as it is used by the international community, especially by World Health Organization.

According to the EUA, a vaccine is registered under the COVAX program at an accelerated rate if its emergency use has been authorized by the competent authority of the United States, the United Kingdom, the Swiss Confederation, Japan, Australia, Canada, the People’s Republic of China or India. At the same time, the measure should be temporary, as untested vaccines can provoke distrust among the population.

Discussion

In the legal field there are discussions about the content and scope of the right to get vaccinated. Most of scientists maintain the position that effective and comprehensive global programme of vaccination should be successfully implemented (Sturgis et al. 2021; Savulescu 2021). COVID-19 once again raises the question: is vaccination a right or a duty of a person? Although no country in the world has so far declared mandatory vaccination against COVID-19, certain trends are already emerging: in Italy, under Article 4 of Decree-Law No. 44 of 1 April 2021, the government has introduced mandatory vaccination against COVID-19 for medical workers. Therefore, the duration of the pandemic, the increased number of vaccines and their availability will encourage the world community to introduce a mandatory vaccination policy against COVID-19.

Conclusions

Nowadays, vaccination is both a right of individual and an obligation, depending on how we interact within society. The researched materials prove that the private interest of an individual to deny vaccination is limited where there is an encroachment on the public interest of the whole population. The legal regulation of vaccination in the EU indeed should be decided on the basis of a balance of private and public interests. Conversely, in the conditions of pandemic, the emphasis shifts to the priorities of society as a whole, its safety and security of those who cannot be vaccinated for medical reasons, and not because of their own reluctance – the health of European society depends on it. Although opponents of mandatory vaccination may refuse it, it is unlikely that the international community will recognize the individual's absolute right to vaccination in the near future.

References

- Acosta J.I. 2015. Vaccines, informed consent, effective remedy and integral reparation: an international human rights perspective. http://www.scielo.org.co/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S004190602015000200002#54 (access 25 April 2021).
- Council of Europe, European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, as amended by Protocols Nos. 11 and 14, 4 November 1950, ETS 5. <https://www.coe.int/ru/web/impact-convention-human-rights/convention-for-the-protection-of-human-rights-and-fundamental-freedoms> (access 30 May 2021).

- Council of Europe, European Social Charter (Revised), 3 May 1996, ETS 163. <https://rm.coe.int/CoERMPublicCommonSearchServices/DisplayDCTMContent?documentId=090000168048b059> (access: 29 May 2021).
- DECRETO-LEGGE 1 aprile 2021, n. 44. Misure urgenti per il contenimento dellepidemia da COVID-19, in materia di vaccinazioni anti SARS-CoV-2, di giustizia e di concorsi pubblici. (21G00056). <https://f.datasrvr.com/fr1/121/57670/DL-1aprile2021-n44.pdf> (access 26 May 2021).
- Demchenko I., Dubitskaya N. Legal regulation of compulsory vaccination: arguments “pro” and “contra”. № 4. 2017. C. 133-138. http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Chkup_2017_4_31 (access 19 April 2021).
- Frankowicz v. Poland, Appl. No. 53025/99, Council of Europe: European Court of Human Rights, 16 December 2008. <http://hudoc.echr.coe.int/fre?i=001-90248> (access 20 April 2021).
- Gubanova O. On the Mechanism of Legal Regulation of Relations in the Field of Immunization. Law Forum № 1. 2017. C. 32–38. http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/FP_index.htm_2017_1_8 (access 26 April 2021).
- Inter-American Court of European Court of Human Rights, ECtHR, Flux v. Moldova, App. No. 22824/04, f 35 (29 July 2008). <http://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng?i=001-88063>. (access 26 April 2021).
- Inter-American Court of Human Rights, IACtHR, Advisory Opinion OC-6/86, The Word “Laws” in Article 30 of the American Convention of Human Rights, Requested by the Government of Uruguay, (May 9, 1986). http://www.corteidh.or.cr/docs/opiniones/seriea_06_ing.pdf (access 26 April 2021).
- Jehovahs Witnesses of Moscow v. Russia, Appl. no. 302/02, Council of Europe: European Court of Human Rights, 10 June 2010. <http://hudoc.echr.coe.int/fre?i=001-99221> (access 20 April 2021).
- Kokkinakis v. Greece, Appl. 14307/88, Council of Europe: European Court of Human Rights, 19 April 1993. <http://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng?i=001-57827> (access 27 April 2021).
- Kruglova O. 2011. Mandatory vaccination: violation of personal non-property rights of an individual. http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/FP_index.htm_2011_1_86 (access 19 April 2021).
- Gostin L., Mann J.M. Toward the Development of a Human Rights Impact Assessment for the Formulation and Evaluation of Public Health Policies, in *Health and Human Rights: A Reader*, p. 67.
- Locke J. 1948.. *The Second Treatise of Civil Government and A Letter Concerning Toleration*. Ch. II (7). B. Blackwell, Oxford, 1632-1704.
- Locke J. 2003. *Two Treatises of Government and A Letter Concerning Toleration*. Ian Shapiro (Ed.). Yale University Press. www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt1npw0d. (access 20 May 2021).
- Montesquieu, Charles de Secondat, baron de, 1689-1755. 1748. *The Spirit of Laws*. London.
- Pretty v. United Kingdom, Appl. no. 2346/02, Council of Europe: European Court of Human Rights, 29 April 2002. <http://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng?i=001-60448> (access: 20 May 2021).
- Questions and Answers: Conditional Marketing Authorisation of COVID-19 Vaccines in the EU. 11 December 2020. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/qanda_20_2390 (access 27 May 2021).
- WHO lists additional COVID-19 vaccine for emergency use and issues interim policy recommendations. 7 May 2021. <https://www.who.int/news/item/07-05-2021-who-lists-additional-covid-19-vaccine-for-emergency-use-and-issues-interim-policy-recommendations#:~:text=WHOs%20Emergency%20Use%20Listing%20> (access 27 May 2021).

- Savin v. Ukraine, Appl. No. 39948/06, Council of Europe: European Court of Human Rights, 12 December 2008. <http://hudoc.echr.coe.int/fre?i=002-1790> (access 27 May 2021).
- Savulescu J. 2021. Good reasons to vaccinate: mandatory or payment for risk? *BMJ Journals*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/medethics-2020-106821> (access 27 May 2021).
- Senyuta I. 2009. Prophylactic vaccinations. The right to medical care in Ukraine. 2008 Kharkiv Human Rights Group. *Human Rights*. pp. 133-142.
- Sturgis P, Brunton-Smith I., Jackson, J. 2021. Trust in science, social consensus and vaccine confidence. *Nat. Hum. Behav.* <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-021-01115-7> (access 27 May 2021).
- UN General Assembly, International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, 16 December 1966, United Nations, Treaty Series, vol. 993, p. 3. <https://www.ohchr.org/en/professionalinterest/pages/cescr.aspx> (access 29 May 2021).
- Vaccine schedules in all countries of the European Union. European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control - agency of the European Union. *Nature*, 2018, 555(7694): 30. <https://vaccine-schedule.ecdc.europa.eu> (access 27 May 2021).
- Vavříčka and Others v. the Czech Republic, Appl. No. 47621/13, Council of Europe: European Court of Human Rights, 8 April 2021. <http://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng?i=001-209039> (access 27 April 2021).
- World Health Organization Coronavirus (COVID-19) Dashboard. <https://covid19.who.int/> (access 19 May 2021).

Abstract

LEGAL ASPECTS OF MANDATORY VACCINATION IN THE EUROPEAN UNION

The article deals with legal aspects of mandatory vaccination in the European Union, and the legality of restrictions on human rights in the field of health care in the conditions of public need to protect the population from the most common diseases is considered.

One of the most effective ways to protect human health is vaccination. Although vaccination of the population is a rather common preventive medical intervention, its side effects, propaganda against vaccination and speculation on public ignorance of its consequences do not improve the situation.

The problem of mandatory vaccination lies within the fact that a state needs to seek balance between the private interest of the person not to be vaccinated and the public interest. The balance of public and private interest, namely the restriction of the rights of the individual for a socially useful purpose, is not a new challenge for law: in the process of fulfilling State's responsibilities, a state may narrow individual freedoms for the sake of society, and that is also applicable to possible mandatory vaccination against COVID-19.

For better coverage of the topic, the author researched numerous sources: doctrine of natural law (a vital component in regard to the fundamental acts of international law, such as the International Covenant on Human Rights and International Pact on Human Rights, are based on these principles), European Court of Human Rights (hereinafter – “The ECtHR”) case law concerning the content of the right to vaccination. The ECtHR case “Vavříčka and Others v. the Czech Republic” of 8 April 2021 is of extreme importance, as the case was the first in which the EU court had ruled on the question of mandatory vaccination.

Research shows that limitation of the private interest to protect public needs is legally justified, because a state endeavours to assure safety of as a whole and of those who cannot be vaccinated for medical reasons.

Key words: right to vaccination, human health, public and private interest, human rights restrictions, European Court of Human Rights

PRAWNE ASPEKTY OBOWIĄZKOWYCH SZCZEPIEŃ W UNII EUROPEJSKIEJ

W artykule omówiono prawne aspekty obowiązkowych szczepień w Unii Europejskiej oraz rozważono legalność ograniczeń praw człowieka w zakresie ochrony zdrowia w warunkach publicznej potrzeby ochrony ludności przed najczęstszymi chorobami.

Jednym z najskuteczniejszych sposobów ochrony zdrowia ludzkiego są szczepienia. Chociaż szczepienie ludności jest dość powszechną profilaktyczną interwencją medyczną, to jej skutki uboczne, propaganda przeciwko szczepieniom i spekulacje na temat nieznamości społecznej ich konsekwencji nie poprawiają sytuacji.

Problem obowiązkowych szczepień polega na tym, że państwo musi dążyć do równowagi między prywatnym interesem osoby, która ma się nie szczepić, a interesem publicznym. Równowaga interesu publicznego i prywatnego, czyli ograniczanie praw jednostki w celu społecznie użytecznym, nie jest nowym wyzwaniem dla prawa: w procesie wypełniania obowiązków państwa może ono zawęzić wolności jednostki na rzecz społeczeństwa i dotyczy to również ewentualnych obowiązkowych szczepień przeciwko COVID-19.

W celu lepszego ujęcia tematu przeanalizowano liczne źródła: na nich opiera się doktryna prawa naturalnego (istotny element w odniesieniu do podstawowych aktów prawa międzynarodowego, takich jak Międzynarodowy Pakt Praw Człowieka i Międzynarodowy Pakt Praw Człowieka), orzecznictwo Europejskiego Trybunału Praw Człowieka (dalej „ETPC”) dotyczące treści prawa do szczepień. Niezwykle ważna jest sprawa ETPC „Vavříčka i inni przeciwko Republice Czeskiej” z 8 kwietnia 2021 r., ponieważ była to pierwsza sprawa, w której sąd UE orzekł w kwestii obowiązkowych szczepień.

Badania pokazują, że ograniczenie interesu prywatnego w celu ochrony potrzeb publicznych jest prawnie uzasadnione, ponieważ państwo dąży do zapewnienia bezpieczeństwa całości oraz tym, którzy nie mogą być zaszczepieni ze względów medycznych.

Słowa kluczowe: prawo do szczepień, zdrowie ludzkie, interes publiczny i prywatny, ograniczenia dotyczące praw człowieka, Europejski Trybunał Praw Człowieka